

Analysis of Historical Sources about the Kushan Kingdom

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Abstract: This article explains the significant changes in the material and spiritual culture of the peoples of Central Asia during the Kushan period. The fate of the Great Kushan Empire ended tragically in terms of its spirituality, that is, its history and culture were practically unwritten in its time. There is very little ancient information about it, and there are not many written monuments.

Keywords: Kattanahor, Zartepa, Zang Canal, Gaofu, yuechji, Han, Karatepa, Peshawar, Guyshuan, Tuyshuan.

Log in. The emergence of the Kushan state has long been the subject of intense scientific debate among scholars. The study of the history of this seemingly legendary kingdom began in the last century. By the 1st century BC, the power of the Tuy Shuan (Kushan) in the five governments of the Greater Yuyechji Association had significantly strengthened and expanded. According to the "History of the Last Han Dynasty" (China), "Klokzuko, the ruler of Guishhuan, merged the remaining four principalities and proclaimed himself ruler of Buishhuan." Among the kings of the Kushan state, the most famous is Kanishka. During his reign, the Kushan Empire further flourished. Under Kanishka, the provinces of Punjab and Kashmir were annexed to the country. The capital of the country was located around Peshawar (Afghanistan). The territory of the country consisted of North India, Afghanistan, many regions of Central Asia, and East Turkestan. According to Sima Zian, "during the reign of Kanishka, his fame spread to neighboring countries." The military power of the country was widely recognized. Those in the western part of China also recognized Kanishka's authority and sent hostages to him.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In Central Asia, BC. In the 4th-2nd centuries BC, Khwarazmian, Parthian, and Sogdian scripts appeared based on the Aramaic script. By the Kushan period, another writing appeared among them - the Kushan (Bactrian) script. The first monuments were discovered in Ayritom and Kuhna Termez in the 1930s and continued in the 1960s. Later, the ancient Buddhist temple of Karatepa near Termez, the ancient towns of Fayaztepa, Khalchayan, and Dalvarzin were opened, and the Kushan culture, which was extremely high, became known throughout the world. Stone images of the ancient city of Ayritom on Mount Kesh (waterfall) were known as early as the 1930s and 1940s. These porticoes were decorated with pictures of girls covered with flowers, playing musical instruments, and children playing drums. In one of the cotton fields of the city of Denau in the Surkhandarya region, the remains of the monument of Khalchayan, which was once a large city, have been preserved. The emergence of cities in BC. It corresponds to the middle of the 1st millennium.

The Greco-Bactrian kingdom, which emerged in 250 BC, included the Surkhan Oasis, along with large areas of Central Asia. During this reign, socio-economic relations developed in Surxondaryo, and class stratification also intensified. The cities prospered. Crafts and foreign trade increased. The cultures of the Greeks, Indians, and Turans blended, creating a unique high culture. The ruins of ancient buildings belonging to this period were also found in the vicinity of Termez.

At the beginning of AD, Surkhandarya became part of the Kushan state. The Kushans initially lived on the territory of the Tokhar state, dividing into 5 tribes for a century. Among them, the Yabguzi (ruler) of the Guishuan (Kushan) tribe, Kudzula Kadfis, subdued the remaining 4 tribes in the 1st century AD and declared himself ruler. At the beginning of AD, the first caravan route from China to the lands of the Kushan kingdom, including Dalvarzintepa, through Termez to the countries of the Mediterranean coast, was one of the southern branches of the Silk Road. This path played a significant role in the development of foreign trade and interstate culture. The Kushan Empire became a centralized slave-owning state. The population mainly believed in the Mahayana mashabe of the Buddhist religion. This is evidenced by the Buddha statue found in Dalvarzintepa. The founder of the Kushan state, Kudzula Kadfis, quickly conquered India and subjugated northern Bactria. Kadfis II, especially during the reign of Kanishka, expanded the Kushan Empire and became a powerful empire comparable in size to the empires of Rome and Parthia Han (China). All of present-day India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and the southern regions of Central Asia were oriented towards it. The Kushan state ruled from the second half of the 1st century BC to the middle of the 3rd century AD.

Archaeological sites dating back to the Kushan period are very numerous and diverse in the Surkhandarya region. From the Achaemenid and Greco-Bactrian periods, 40 target cities have been known here so far, and more than 120 cities and villages dating back to the Kushan period have been identified. The population was mainly located along the Sherabad and Surkhandarya basins. Large small towns and settlements were located around the central cities in the irrigation basins, which were subordinate to the center in all respects. The central cities, in turn, were subordinate to the largest city in Surxondaryo - Termez. Thus, settlements were divided into large cities (Chaganiyan, Termez), medium cities (Dalvarzintepa, Zartepa), and small towns (Jondavlattepa, Talashgantepa, etc.) into large and small villages. Of the 120 monuments found, 40 can be attributed to large cities.

The Kushan Empire, which ruled from the 1st to the 3rd centuries BC, is considered one of the states that played an important role not only in the history of our Motherland, but also in the economic and cultural development of the peoples of the historical regions of Central Asia. The tribes that founded the Kushan kingdom were called yuechji (yovchi) and tokhar in historical sources. In the fourth quarter of the 2nd century BC, the Greco-Bactrian kingdom, which ruled mainly in Bactria, collapsed due to the migration of the yuechji tribes living in the northern regions of Central Asia. By the 1st century AD, the yuechji tribes living in Bactria, divided into five large clans (Hyūmi, Shuanmi, Guishū, Heitun, and Gaofu - or Dumī instead of Gaofu in another source), were united into a single state under the Guishūan-Kushon clan by Kudzula Kadfiz.

The northern boundary of the Kushan state was Baysuntau, part of the South Gissar mountain range, and the Kushan rulers also worked tirelessly to strengthen the northern borders of their state.

One of such structures is the "Temir Darvoza" in Baysuntau and the defensive fortifications associated with it. Under the rule of Vima Kadfiz and especially Kanishka I, the lands of Northern India and East Turkestan were included in this state, and as a result, the Kushan state became a great state alongside the Roman Empire of the Old World, Parthia, and Han

China. At the end of the 3rd century AD, due to internal conflicts and especially the occupation of Kushan city, that is, Bactria, by Sasanian Iranian troops, the Kushan state collapsed.

The existence of a centralized state for four centuries led to an upsurge in all aspects of economic and cultural life in Bactria, including the Surkhan Oasis, which was its constituent part.

In the 1st century BC - 1st century AD, the Surkhan Oasis was rapidly developed, large canals were dug (Kattanahar), existing irrigation facilities were expanded (Zang Canal), new cities were founded (Zartepa) or cities such as Termez (Termiz) and Dalvarzintepa expanded in terms of territory. The cities of the Kushan period consisted of two parts built according to the project, namely the ark A'lo and the adjacent parts of the main city. The urban planning of this period was well-studied through the religious structures of Dalvarzintepa, Zartepa, Kuhna Termez, and its constituent parts, Karatepa, Fayaztepa.

The cities of the Kushan period of the Surkhan oasis served as administrative and economic centers, as well as religious centers (Buddhist temples in Karatepa, Fayaztepa, Zartepa, Ayritom, and Dalvarzintepa in Old Termez). At the very beginning of Kushan rule, the intercontinental trade route, the Great Silk Road, which economically and culturally linked the states and peoples of the Ancient World, was fully formed, and the Kushan state also played an important role in this international trade.

The monuments excavated in such monuments as Khalchayan, Dalvarzintepa, Kuhna Termez, Zartepa, Ayritom, created in secular and religious directions, various types of miniature art, and various handicrafts are distinguished by their unique nature.

The city of Jizzakh served as a gateway between major cities such as Siberia, Kazakhstan, Shash, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khorasan. In ancient times, three caravan routes, crossing the Mirzachul through Fergana, Uratapa, and Zaamin, and passing straight through Kazakhstan to Nurata, were joined in Jizzakh and passed from the Ilonutdy Gorge to the Samarkand Gorge, and then to the oasis. The gates and fortresses at the entrance of these roads to Jizzakh were built during the Kushan Empire, that is, in the 1st-4th centuries. Therefore, the name of the city is also related to the names of those fortresses.

The original name of this castle was Dizak. The same is written in written sources from the 10th century. According to the scientific conclusions of scientists studying place names, "Diz" means "fortress," "fortress" in ancient Sogdian, and "ak" corresponds to the affix "cha" in our language.

So, Dyzak means "fortress." It can also be said that in the 12th-17th centuries, there were villages called Upper Dizak and Lower Dizak in Khorasan. The Arab geographer and traveler al-Maqdissi wrote about the city of Dyzak: "It is a big city, a river flows through it, and there is a mosque in its market." The work "Hudud al-Alam," written in 983, states that "Jizzakh is a small city located on the water's edge, there is a market nearby, and there is a large trade." The books "Surkhandarya," "Termiz," as well as textbooks for students, detail the hum, basin, jug, dagger, sword, pottery, simple jewelry, and coins of the Kushan period.

We only knew the scientific conclusion of archaeologist M. Masson, E. Pugachenkova and other archaeologists. However, in recent years, finds related to the Buddhist religion have also begun to interest everyone. The remains of the Buddha's temple near the town of Dalvarzintepa attracted the attention of the peoples of the world to these findings. When this exhibition of artifacts was presented in Nara, Japan, the citizens of the Land of the Rising Sun were amazed. After all, they belong to the Buddhist religion. Furthermore, the Buddhist objects found in the cities of Khalchayan and Budrach near Dalvarzintepa increased their admiration.

The Japanese's interest in the findings of Dalvarzintepa, Khalchayan, and Budrach increased not only because of the Buddha temple, the Buddha's head, and the giant statue of Bodysatva. Perhaps other examples also attracted the attention of the Japanese to us - Uzbekistan, in particular, Surkhandarya. They hoped that many more Buddha-related information could be found in the ruins of these places.

In 2003-2006, archaeologists from Japan, Russia, France, and Germany arrived in Surxondaryo and continued excavations of Dalvarzintepa, Khalchayan, Budrach, Eski Termez, Kampirtepa, Fayaztepa, Karatepa, and other monuments, as well as "diagnosing" long-term research. The scientists of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek and Termez State University were at the forefront of these studies. Among them were graduate student of the National University of Uzbekistan Jaloliddin Annaev, teacher of Termez State University, candidate of historical sciences Tukhtash Annaev, director of the Surkhandarya Archaeological Museum Ismail Botirov and other scientists. Thus, a Buddhist temple, a statue of Bodysatva, and other objects were also found in Fayaztepa. Most importantly, this temple occupied a large area, so scientists recognized it as the best find in Buddhism. Eventually, it was decided that Buddhism spread from there to China, India, and Japan. Therefore, in collaboration with the Ministry of Culture and Sports of Uzbekistan, the UNESCO representative office in our republic, and the Japanese scientific and cultural centers, a small specimen of this found temple was built in Fayoztepa.

The land of Surkhan is very rich in monuments. Scientific research indicates that four to five thousand years ago, agriculture and crafts were extremely developed in the oasis, and the art and culture of the Kushan, Bactrian, and Chaganian states were at a good level. It is said that even at that time, irrigation structures and even pipelines were used, which testifies to the high intelligence of our ancestors. However, it is known that Buddhism also developed in the 2nd and 2nd millennia BC. To everyone's surprise, before the completion of archaeological excavations in Fayaztepa, a Buddhist temple, a Buddha statue, and other material evidence were found in the village next to it, that is, in Karatepa. In particular, the Buddhist candlestick burned. The antiquity of these sites has been proven by artifacts previously discovered at the Dalvarzintepa, Khalchayan, Budrach, Kampirtepa, Djarkutan, and Eski Termez excavations. The same opinion is shared by the archaeologist Eduard Rtvladze, the Japanese historian and archaeologist Kyūzō Kato. Even Queso Cato, when he saw the thorn-flower, wept with joy. He sang the national anthem of Japan, confessed his Buddha findings, and even at the age of 84, he behaved like a child. Why, you say? Because if this temple, statue and other objects are really evidence and prove that Buddhism began here, not only the Japanese, but even other people belonging to the Buddhist religion, like Chinese and Indians, will come here and worship. Kyūzō Kato had left for Japan with the intention of announcing news in Japan, publishing it in the annual magazine *Oyxonum*, and organizing an exhibition based on new finds. He will soon return to Surkhandarya and continue his work.

"I am eighty-four years old, I have lived my life," he said to me on his way home. But because I participated in the Karatepa excavations, I will be happy even if I die." By the way, Faizhtepa and Karatepa speak and clarify many things, which is a clear proof that the Uzbek and Japanese peoples have lived in friendship and harmony since ancient times.

Conclusions and suggestions. On the territory of Central Asia, including Tajikistan, primitive humans lived about 200,000 years ago. Late Paleolithic tools have been found in northern and southern Tajikistan. The primitive communal system existed in Tajikistan until the 8th-7th centuries BC. The transition to the Iron Age began in the 8th-7th centuries BC. Social and property stratification arose. In the 6th-4th centuries BC, the Iranian state was established in Tajikistan. At the beginning of our era, large irrigation canals were built, urban life and crafts reached a high level, and trade with other countries developed rapidly. Based on the Greek script, the Kushan script appeared. During this period, Buddhism from India and

Manichaeism from Iran entered Tajikistan. But Zoroastrianism remained the main religion. In the middle of the 6th century, Tajikistan was incorporated into the Turkic Khaganate. By the middle of the 8th century, Central Asia had been conquered by the Arabs. As a result of the Arab conquest of Central Asia, Islam became the dominant religion, and many cultural monuments and cities were destroyed. The economic and cultural development of the peoples of Central Asia temporarily slowed down. Several Buddhist monuments in Northern Bactria - Ayritom, Fayaztepa, and Karatepa - were found in reliable stratigraphic conditions. All of this allows for the following reconstruction of the process of Buddhism's spread in Central Asia. It is likely that some Buddhist preachers began spreading this doctrine in Bactria in the 2nd and 1st centuries BC. However, the mass construction of Buddhist religious structures in northern Bactria, and consequently, the spread of the doctrine in the region, can only be attributed to the second half of the 1st century AD. This is explained by the fact that Bactria, as well as India at that time, was part of a single Kushan state.

Archaeological materials indicate that Old Termez was one of the largest centers of Buddhism in the region.

It is located 120 kilometers northeast of Old Termez (now in the Shurchi district). About 36 kg of gold treasure, ancient chess pieces, a house of artisans and potters, some temples, a Dalvarzin cemetery - a novus, 2 wonderful Buddhist structures found in Dalvarzintepa indicate that this city was once the first capital city of the Kushan Empire. The Buddhist temple in Dalvarzinda was first discovered in 1967. The coins found on the monument were minted during the reign of the Kushan king Kadfiz I (1st century AD). The Kushan king of the 2nd century BC, Vasudeva, minted a coin depicting himself on a kulah. The second temple in Dalvarzine is larger than the Buddhist temple outside the city. Excavations began here in 1983. The large Buddha and Badhisatva statues found were made based on the traditions accepted in all areas where Buddhism was spread, the Gandhara School of Buddhist Sculpture in northwest India. In the second half of the 2nd century BC, according to Chinese sources, the Yuezhi tribes (actually the Massagetae) living in the territories of Eastern Turkestan, being oppressed by their neighbors the Huns, could not withstand their pressure and moved westwards. The Yuezhi encountered the Saka tribes around Issyk-Kul and pushed them southwest. However, the yuechjis, being hit by the usun tribes, moved south and entered the territory of Sogdiana around 130 BC. The Yuezhi, according to Chinese historian Zhang Qian, marched from Sogdiana to Bactria and overthrew Greek rule in Bactria. As noted in Chinese sources, the Yuezhi belonged to five main families: Guishuan (Kushon), Humi, Shuanmi, Hise, and Dumi. Each of them has been a separate political force, power, and functioning independently of a single ruler for almost 100 years.

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